

New Christendom

The Problem

Christianity - or rather Christendom itself - is failing. It isn't reaching young people at sustainable rates. Christians (by birth) are denying God, or the Resurrection, citing atheist or other arguments based in semi-scientific facts, but mostly anti-scientific paradigms (such as the Dark Universe/Big Bang, etc.) and cosmologies which deny the evidence in the rock and histories of mankind. The schism of mind, body, spirit, and soul is not merely Cartesian, or Aristotelian, it is downright anti-Renaissance, and even denies the uniqueness of mankind (and other sentience), claiming coincidence and other fallacies.

The resultant is a decay of marriage, family, Western Civilization, honor, justice, education, medicine (away from the barbaric), morality and the noble purpose of Science. This is because Science inherently is not designed to have a moral center, it is presumed a wise scientist of good birth will bring this with him. But increasingly science is commanded by non-Christian centers, and in fact may now be centered in what could be termed nearly purely Asiatic centers, where the stream of consciousness of the Great Enlightenment and its great Christian thinkers has no sway. Christendom begins to leak, like a ship with many holes in its vessel. Preachers embezzle, deacons have affairs, bishops cover up for pedophilia, and the entire ship begins to sink. People get off, and abandon Christ, though He has never abandoned them.

The Query

In the era of STEM, is there a way to engineer the New Religion, specifically a New Christendom (as a first step), to reverse or stem the decay, or at least provide an alternative vessel for those who are not without faith but merely losing hope in the typical power and bureaucratic structures which are foundering? Post-COVID, is there a way to reconnect people in a meaningful way to the Holy Spirit which has been typically (or maybe only) experienced in a non-digital (analog, perhaps) way?

The Solution

The author proposes a series of Bible additions which are carefully constructed to include the permanent truths of the Holy Bible, and add to them, in the way the early church did, (such as Paul, or Simon Peter), which include the items which currently beset mankind. Not in a too time-dependent or datable way, and yet, not without a concept of modern science, chemistry, and the electromagnetic and plasma cosmologies which reveal so much about the Father's plans for mankind. The design of the church (so to speak) to be capable of moving through the social media and internet systems, providing moral inoculations for people questing for Christ in a depraved, digital landscape.

The Caveat

The new paradigm, new evangelism, new protestantism will be constrained to *not* turn off (excepting obvious bigotry and traditional biases) traditional forms of Christianity. It should be capable of performing well in mixed audiences, while avoiding all cultism and extremism, as well as the trappings of communes and egotism.

The Quest

The resultant quest will be primarily for the right words, received by the Holy Spirit himself, as well as the subsequent data which avoid the lies of Satan's agendas, and to put these into written, digital form (despite being analog). Also the quests of the individual shall needs be respected, realizing that a plague of

pan-spiritualism, which does not actually support the entire 5-color-path wheel¹ but erodes it in the name of hedonism, is all too ever-present.

The Quench

The quench, in a sword-making context, is the hardening and rapid cooling of the sword, in order to forge it properly. It is done with water or oil. Both of these are Christian substances as well, so the analogy is complete. What this would imply is that the information would need to heat up the spirits of the readers, listeners (to podcast sermons etc.) and then quench their thirst for the Lord, quench their needs to redeem themselves, cleanse their souls, harden them against the corruption of the world, and prepare them for the upcoming difficulties. In other words, teach a world of sinners to rely on their faith in the invisible but omnipresent God, who is their father, Lord, savior, and Creator. And it will need to do all this hammering and quenching in a quicker manner than the “flash in a pan” instant gratification results of social media vanity fadism, or other classical temptations (criminality, debauchery, etc.).

The Crusade

In the mid-20th century Billy Graham set the world ablaze with his Holy Crusade and reached hundreds of millions of people over a 50-year timespan. But in a few short years his work being on YouTube could easily surpass this work. This is the leverage of technology and archiving. Similarly, a properly leveraged viral campaign that was designed to touch at the neural synapses of the thirsty and hungry could reach potentially billions of people, and prepare them, or at least, hopefully, get them to *conceive* of a desire for salvation and a relationship with God and specifically with Christ our Lord and savior.

It would be a digital Holy Crusade, the first of its kind. It would need, however, to take advantage of the newest software, data², and world/cultural information to subsume other cultures, and sidestep overly divisive cultural barriers. Christ is for everyone and not westerners alone. He can bring people peace whether they be from the jungle, the plains, the cities of Asia or Africa, etc. Ideally it could even convert aliens, if they are real and interested in mankind. Such a virality should be capable of quenching the lusts of violence, hatred, bigotry, and greed that plague modern mankind just as they did before (only nowadays people have the potential to do far more harm).

The Redemption

By redeeming the Word of Christ for new digital generations, it is perhaps feasible to prepare mankind to work together not in a utopian/dystopian fantasy of globalized power in the hands of a few... but instead prepare millions to billions of people for the reality of mortality and that we all need to work together and accept our brotherhood, even if we are so vastly different as night and day. To be able to tolerate even intolerable behaviors, with love, and yet be firm and know the Holiness of God! The Catholic Church in the days of Jesuits forcefully converted hundreds of millions of heathens, and this was good for a time to stop human sacrifice. But that isn't the way we can crusade now, nor is it able to redeem Christendom's past sins for the future.

If we want Christendom to survive the digital revolutions, then we will have to do so in a morally superior manner (to our modern past). We must borrow from the Buddhists the concept of the “friend in the orchid room” and present, but do not expect. After a time people will know a digital convert, or others affected positively downstream by digital conversion, and these Newly Christened converts will, with great effort, be able to present themselves lovingly to those of difference. We may not eliminate the Devil or his wars... but we may in fact spark the seeds of change in people's hearts and minds that enables them to question or overthrow dark powers which pervert God's creation for wicked endeavors. Yet we must never allow the virality to include cult-like behaviors, judgment (in place of the Lord) and condemnation, envy and spite, and the wallowing in self-pity and self-destruction that currently plague western civilization.

¹ God made red, yellow, white, black and brown people to represent Fire, Earth, Metal, Water, and Wood, respectively.

² The most powerful data God has ever made: 0,1,1,2,3,5,8,13... In this is coded God's very plan for us and our bodies.